

The DJ-as-researcher Approach: Methods Emerging Through Digital Cumbia Fieldwork

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Abstract. This presentation reflects on research methods which have emerged from fieldwork exploring the roots of digital cumbia music, in the sonidera culture of Mexico. The fieldwork has included physical travel to Mexico and other countries where digital cumbia emerged, but the bulk of it has been based online. The argument presented is that online fieldwork is as equally valid as physical fieldwork, and is supported by the digital ethnography research of anthropologist John Postill, who has outlined four fundamental ways of being in the field in this digital age: physically, remotely, virtually, and imaginatively.

These ways of being in the field reflect the experience of the participants in the sonidera culture being researched, as well as the author's extensive experience as a DJ of digital cumbia. Whilst the research employs methods well-established in ethnomusicology – participant observation and interviews – the approach is led by the author's extensive experience as a DJ of digital cumbia, leading to what the author is calling the DJ-as-researcher approach. It is multi-sited, performative, and communicated via social media. Posting updates on the research using #cumbiaresearch on the author's social media profiles as a DJ, providing ongoing on- and offline engagement with research participants. Using a mobile phone camera to film interviews and during participant observation, became an expectation of the research participants. Live streaming of interviews emerged as being beneficial to both researcher and research participants, as it communicated the research to a broader public and added to the social media profiles of both the researcher and the researched. Ultimately, this approach facilitates a high degree of 'giving back' or 'reciprocity', and builds an ongoing network of research collaborators, and grassroots, community-based organizations run by DJs, doing archival and advocacy projects. In this way, the multi-sited, highly mediated and collaborative DJ-as-researcher approach reflects the sociocultural complexity which links digital cumbia and sonidero culture. Like people coming together on the dancefloor, this approach has the potential to cut through perceived and very real boundaries of geography, ethnicity, and class, that can divide the researcher from the researched.

Moses Iten is PhD candidate at RMIT University in Melbourne, Australia, researching digital cumbia music and Mexican sound system culture. Professional DJ/producer for more than a decade, and with his Cumbia Cosmonauts project has toured all over the world. Research interests and DJ practice collide in his various roles as a participant with the initiatives Cumbia Massive (Melbourne, Australia), Centro de Cumbia Experimental (Buenos Aires, Argentina), Centro de Documentacion de la Cumbia (Monterrey, Mexico), Sound System Outernational (London, UK); and as a member of the RMIT-based research groups Screen & Sound Cultures and the Digital Ethnography Research Centre (DERC). Moses worked for many years as a radio host, and has produced numerous music-based feature documentaries for ABC Radio National. More recently, Moses organised the first Global South Popular Music Perspectives (2020) symposium at RMIT, and assisted in translating the book *Ojos Suaves/Soft Eyes: Sound System Cumbia from Mexico to the World* (2017) by Mirjam Wirz. Moses works in the languages of English, Spanish, German and French, and has a Master of Community Cultural Development from the Victorian College of the Arts (University of Melbourne) and a Bachelor of Arts in Communication (Journalism) & International Studies (Mexico) from the University of Technology, Sydney.

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